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CROHN'S DISEASE ORIGIN, CAUSES AND TREATMENT METHODS

***Abstract.** In this article, we will learn about Crohn's disease. In addition, in this article, we will learn about the causes of Crohn's disease, the clinic and treatment methods. they are supposed to have information.*

***Key words:** Crohn's disease, severe diarrhea, fatigue, diet, stress, immune system, virus, colonoscopy, steroid, anaphylactic shock, biological drug, operation.*

Crohn's disease is a type of inflammatory bowel disease. This causes inflammation of the gastrointestinal tract, which can cause abdominal pain, severe diarrhea, fatigue, weight loss, and poor nutrition. The inflammation caused by Crohn's disease affects digestion in different people. can cover different areas of the tract. This inflammation often spreads to the deeper layers of the intestine. Crohn's disease can be both painful and debilitating, and can sometimes lead to life-threatening complications. People between the ages of 16 and 40 suffer more from Crohn's disease. For information, it should be said that 20% of patients with Crohn's disease also have this disease in their close relatives. We can point to immunological or bacteriological problems as the cause of the disease. This disease is not contagious. X-rays are taken of the intestines to diagnose it. Although there is no known cure for the disease, therapy can significantly reduce its signs and symptoms and even lead to long-term remission and healing of inflammation. By treating patients with this disease, they get rid of the pain and discomfort observed during the illness. Crohn's disease can occur anywhere in the small or large intestine, and it can be continuous or involve multiple segments. In some people, the disease is limited to the large intestine, which is a part of the large intestine. The symptoms of the disease can be mild to severe. They usually develop gradually, but sometimes they appear suddenly without warning. You may also have periods when you have no symptoms (remission). The exact cause of Crohn's disease remains unknown. In the past, diet and stress were suspected, but now doctors know that these factors can exacerbate Crohn's disease, but not cause it. Several factors such as heredity and malfunction of the immune system play a role in its development. Immune system. A virus or bacteria can cause this disease; however, scientists have not yet been able to identify such a trigger. When your immune system tries to fight off an invading microorganism, an abnormal immune response causes the immune system to attack cells in your digestive system as well.

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Heredity. Crohn's disease is more common in people with a family history of the disease, so genes may play a role in making people more susceptible. However, most people with Crohn's disease do not have a family history of the disease. Crohn's disease is caused by a number of factors, including epigenetic, immunological, and bacterial. The result is a chronic inflammatory process in which the body's immune system attacks the gastrointestinal tract - presumably to fight off what it thinks are microbial antibodies. This condition is partly due to a weakened immune system, and genes play a role in the disease. has been identified. Smoking is associated with a doubling of the risk of Crohn's disease. Diagnosis is based on a series of studies, including biopsy, imaging, and a complete medical history. Other differential diagnoses include irritable bowel syndrome and Behcet's disease. A colonoscopy is recommended regularly (once a year) 1 year after diagnosis - to check for colon cancer and the like. Crohn's disease is currently incurable. The goal of treatment is to control inflammation and relieve symptoms, including abdominal pain and diarrhea, and keep your child at an appropriate pace. Therapy makes it possible to achieve a state without symptoms, that is, remission of the disease, which can last for many years. However, the disease usually grows and recurs, and the whole procedure must be started from the beginning, which is associated with long-term specialist help and periodic examinations. Patients are often treated with:

1. steroids,
2. anti-inflammatory drugs and drugs that modulate the immune system.

Sometimes surgery is necessary. However, there is a group of patients for whom such treatment is ineffective. So-called biological drugs. In the production of biological drugs, scientists used the natural mechanism of the human body - the ability to create antibodies against viruses, bacteria or other factors that cause disease. Lymphocytes, or white blood cells, have this ability. Without them, the simplest infection could be fatal for people. Lymphocytes produce a protein that kills the invader that attacks the body. Thus, they created transgenic mice implanted with human genes, as a result of which their lymphocytes were "humanized". Human lymphocytes created in the body of mice were introduced to various pathogens. When given to patients, the trained lymphocytes produce antibodies that block the factors responsible for inflammation. Unfortunately, these drugs are not perfect and have side effects. First of all, they can cause allergic reactions, even anaphylactic shock, and sometimes infections with a very severe course. Therefore, when deciding to use these drugs, the risk-benefit ratio should be taken into account. They are the drug of last resort in patients who are not helped by standard therapy. Another problem is that the program can only treat biological drugs for a year and in a very strict regimen. - This is a decision based on the state of the science 10 years ago when short-term therapy was considered sufficient. Today, it is known that Crohn's disease is chronic, requires long-term treatment with doses adapted to the needs of the patient, and only a doctor knows when to stop therapy, explains Dr. Sladek. In addition, relapse

means the loss of the condition obtained as a result of biological therapy, which is often associated with the further, dangerous development of the disease. Few parents can buy drugs for their children, because the price of one dose is several or even a few thousand zlotys, and the drug is used every 8 weeks. Meanwhile, a child who receives biological drugs does not have to stay in the hospital for a long time, goes to kindergarten or school, actively participates in life with peers, and is free of symptoms of the disease. Incorrectly treated Crohn's disease hinders the child's development, interferes with social functioning and increases the risk of surgery, which is also expensive and primarily leads to disability, such as the appearance of a stoma or short bowel syndrome. In addition, such a patient may require parenteral nutrition in the future, which is also expensive. Often he receives disability benefits.

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